

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL TO “INTRASEASONAL TEMPERATURE VARIABILITY IN A SHELF-INCISED VALLEY IN THE SOUTHWESTERN TROPICAL ATLANTIC”

This supplementary section provides the methodological background for the Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD), Hilbert spectrum, and Time-Dependent Intrinsic Correlation (TDIC) approaches applied in the main manuscript. Because the temperature and forcing records analyzed here are nonlinear and nonstationary, these methods were adopted to isolate variability at different time scales, describe its time-varying energetic expression, and evaluate scale-dependent correlations between temperature and external forcings. The purpose of this section is to summarize the theoretical basis of each method and clarify how they complement one another within the analytical framework of this study. EEMD was used to decompose the original series into intrinsic mode functions, the Hilbert transform was used to estimate instantaneous frequency and energy, and TDIC was used to examine the temporal evolution of correlations between selected temperature and forcing modes. The derivations and concepts presented below are intended to support the interpretation of the results shown in the main text.

S1 – METHODOLOGICAL BACKGROUND OF THE EEMD, HILBERT SPECTRUM, AND TDIC APPROACHES

To understand the theoretical basis for the EEMD, one must first understand its precursor, the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD).

Natural time series often display nonlinear and nonstationary characteristics, which are not well captured by most traditional methods such as Fourier transform or wavelet analysis, both of which rely on linearity and/or stationarity assumptions (Franzke, 2009; Huang and Schmitt, 2014; Kbaier et al., 2016). To address this, the EMD was developed as an adaptive, a posteriori empirical technique capable of decomposing such complex signals into a set of intrinsic oscillatory modes, known as Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs). Like empirical orthogonal function (EOF) analysis, EMD decomposes the signal into functions derived from the data itself. However, unlike EOFs, the EMD yields temporal modes rather than spatial ones, making it particularly suitable for analyzing time-dependent variability. This method is particularly effective for nonlinear and nonstationary natural data (Wu and Huang, 2009; Huang and Schmitt, 2014) such as the ocean temperature series observed in this study.

Each IMF satisfies two conditions: (1) the number of extrema and the number of zero crossings must be equal or differ at most by one, and (2) at any point, the mean value of the upper and lower envelopes – defined respectively by the local maxima and minima – must be zero (Huang et al., 1998). These IMFs form the basis for analyzing variability across different timescales. Lower-order IMFs, which capture higher-frequency content, typically represent short-term processes such as tidal forcing, local wind mixing, or turbulence. Higher-order IMFs often correspond to longer-term processes like seasonal variability, remote atmospheric forcing, or large-scale oceanographic phenomena (e.g., Rossby waves or mesoscale eddies), depending on the length of the original time series. This decomposition enables the separation and interpretation of the multiple dynamic components that influence a system.

The IMFs from the time series $x(t)$ are obtained through an iterative process that begins with the identification of the local extrema (maxima and minima) of the signal. The local maxima (minima) are connected by a spline to form the upper (lower) envelope of the function. Then, we obtain the average function of this envelope (m_1). The difference between the original signal $x(t)$ and the average function of this envelope (m_1) is called the first proto mode h_1 (Eq. 3).

$$h_1 = x(t) - m_1 \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

The process is repeated (sifting process) until the remaining signal meets conditions of an IMF presented above. That is, the proto mode h_1 is treated as the data in the following iteration (Eq. 4).

$$h_1 - m_{11} = h_{11} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

After k iterations (Eq. 5), h_{1k} becomes the first IMF, c_1 (Eq. 6).

$$h_{1(k-1)} - m_{1k} = h_{1k} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

$$c_1 = h_{1k} \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

The sifting process separates the finest local mode from the data based only on the characteristic time scale. Nonetheless, performing sifting the process to an extreme could make the resulting IMF a pure frequency modulated signal of constant amplitude, eliminating the physically meaningful amplitude fluctuations (Huang *et al.*, 1998). To avoid this, Huang *et al.* (1998) determined a criterion for the sifting process to stop. This criterion can be achieved by limiting the size of the standard deviation (SD), computed from the two consecutive sifting results, the same as the Cauchy's convergence criteria (Eq. 7). A typical value for SD can be set between 0.2 and 0.3.

$$SD = \sum_{t=0}^T \left[\frac{|h_{1(k-1)}(t) - h_{1k}(t)|^2}{h_{1(k-1)}^2(t)} \right] \quad (\text{Equation 7})$$

After the convergence criterion is reached, c_1 should contain the finest scale or the shortest period component of the signal. We can then separate c_1 from the rest of the data by Eq. 8.

$$x(t) - c_1 = r_1 \quad (\text{Equation 8})$$

Now r_1 is the residue that still contains information of longer-period components. It is treated as new data and subjected to the same sifting process described above. This procedure can be repeated on all the subsequent r_j , and the result is:

$$r_1 - c_2 = r_2, \dots, r_{n-1} - c_n = r_n \quad (\text{Equation 9})$$

The iteration can be stopped by any of the following predetermined criteria: either (a) when the component, c_n , or the residue, r_n , becomes so small that it is less than the predefined threshold, or (b) when the residue, r_n , becomes a monotonic function from which no more IMFs can be extracted. Even for zero-mean data, the final residue may be nonzero; for data with a trend, the final residue represents that trend. By summing up Eq. 8 and Eq. 9, we finally obtain Eq. 10. Thus, we achieved a decomposition of the data into n-empirical modes, and a residue, r_n , which can be either the mean trend or a constant.

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i - r_n \quad (\text{Equation 10})$$

However, one of the major drawbacks of the EMD is the mode mixing, which is defined as a single IMF either consisting of signals of widely disparate scales, or a signal of a similar scale observed in different IMF components (Wu and Huang, 2009). The Ensemble EMD (EEMD) was formulated by Wu and Huang (2009) to decrease the mode-mixing issue. It is based on the EMD with the additional application of the noise-assisted data analysis. In this method we add a white Gaussian noise $w_n(t)$ to the original data $x(t)$ as in Eq. 11 and then decompose the noise data $x_n(t)$ with the standard EMD. We perform several (N) trials with varying noise ensembles $w_n(t)$.

$$x_n(t) = x(t) + w_n(t) \quad (\text{Equation 11})$$

At the end of the trials, the final IMFs are obtained as the ensemble mean across trials (Eq. 12). In this manner, with enough number of trials, statistically, the added noise cancels out in the ensemble result.

$$imf(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N imf_n(t) \quad (\text{Equation 12})$$

In EEMD, the number of ensembles and the noise amplitude are the two parameters that need to be prescribed. In this work we used an ensemble number of 100 and a noise amplitude about 0.2 times the data standard deviation, as recommended by Wu and Huang (2009).

After verifying that the components extracted from the temperature time series met the criteria for IMFs (Wu and Huang, 2009), we analyzed the variance associated with each IMF to quantify the relative contribution of different processes to the overall variability of the signal. We focused on IMFs whose average variance exceeded 5%, to capture the most significant components of temperature variability. These IMFs were also used to compute the Hilbert spectrum, which represents the energy content across time scales (i.e., frequencies) as a function of time (Huang *et al.*, 1998).

The Hilbert spectrum was obtained by passing the resulting IMFs as arguments for the "hht" function from MATLAB that computes the spectrum of a signal using Hilbert-Huang Transform. For any IMF $x(t)$, its Hilbert

transform $y(t)$ is given by the Eq. 13 where P denotes the Cauchy principal value.

$$y(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} P \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x(\tau)}{t-\tau} d\tau \quad (\text{Equation 13})$$

With the Hilbert transform $y(t)$ of the function $x(t)$, we obtain the analytic function given by Eq. 14, where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, a is the instantaneous amplitude given by $a(t) = (x^2 + y^2)^{1/2}$ and θ is the instantaneous phase function given by $\theta(t) = \tan^{-1} \frac{y}{x}$.

$$z(t) = x(t) + iy(t) = a(t)e^{i\theta(t)} \quad (\text{Equation 14})$$

The instantaneous frequency is given by Eq. 15.

$$\omega = \frac{d\theta}{dt} \quad (\text{Equation 15})$$

With both amplitude and frequency being a function of time, we can express the amplitude (or energy, the square of amplitude) in terms of a function of time and frequency, $H(\omega, t)$. The marginal spectrum can then be defined by Eq. 16 where $[0, T]$ is the temporal domain within which the data is defined.

$$h(\omega) = \int_0^T H(\omega, t) dt \quad (\text{Equation 16})$$

The marginal spectrum represents the accumulated amplitude (energy) over the entire data span in a probabilistic sense and offers a measure of the total amplitude (or energy) contribution from each frequency value, serving as an alternative spectrum expression of the data to the traditional Fourier spectrum. The Hilbert spectrum is similar to the wavelet energy spectrum, however the first presents a better resolution than the latter (see Kbaier et al., 2016 for the comparison between the two methods).

TDIC is used to quantify the dynamic relationships between two time series considering the nonstationary and nonlinear nature of the data by focusing on time-varying correlations at specific IMFs. It is based on the correlation over time of two IMFs of different variables, with similar frequencies, on various time scales (i.e., time windows). The time-varying correlation is given by Eq. 17, where c_{1i} and c_{2i} are the two IMFs investigated, t_w^n is the time window for the correlation, given by Eq. 18 and n is any real positive number. The minimum window for calculating local correlation is given by Eq. 19, where T_{1i} and T_{2i} are the instantaneous periods of the two IMFs obtained through the zero-crossing method.

$$R_i(t_k^n) = \text{Corr}(c_{1i}(t_w^n), c_{2i}(t_w^n)) \quad (\text{Equation 17})$$

$$t_w^n = [t_k - nt_d/2; t_k + nt_d/2] \quad (\text{Equation 18})$$

$$t_d = (T_{1i}(t_k), T_{2i}(t_k)) \quad (\text{Equation 19})$$

To determine the statistical significance of the correlation coefficients, TDIC applies the Student's t-test where we considered $p \leq 0.05$ statistically significant (i.e., at the 95% confidence level). The result is a correlation matrix with statistical significance over time (x-axis) for each time window used to calculate the correlation index (y-axis) (Chen et al., 2010). This correlation matrix is filtered so cells with $p > 0.05$ are marked as non-significant, and those with $p \leq 0.05$ are retained for interpretation and visualization. This mask ensures that only the statistically supported correlations are considered in the final TDIC plot (Chen et al., 2010).

The schematic Figure S1 illustrates the methodological steps applied to analyze the multiscale structure and temporal relationships between two temperature time series using EEMD, Hilbert spectral analysis, TDIC. Two time series with nonstationary and nonlinear characteristics that are not easily captured by traditional linear decomposition techniques are shown in the top panels (Figure S1a). Each time series is decomposed via EEMD into a set of IMFs, which represent oscillatory modes embedded in the original signal (Figure S1b). The IMFs are then used to compute the Hilbert Spectrum (e.g., time series 2 in Figure S1c), which expresses the signal's energy distribution in the time–frequency domain.

Figure S1. Schematic representation of the methodology applied to investigate the multiscale structure and interrelations between two time series. (a) Two temperature time series are decomposed using the Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD) method, yielding a set of variability modes known as (b) Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs). (c) The Hilbert Spectrum for the IMFs from time series 2 is obtained. (d) To explore the temporal dynamics of a specific mode, the fifth IMF (C5) from each time series is selected for further comparison, as they exhibit similar frequency modulation patterns and explain a significant fraction of the total variance. (e) The selected IMFs are shown superimposed in the time domain (right panel) and compared using the Time Dependent Intrinsic Correlation (TDIC) method (left panel). In the TDIC output The color shading represents the correlation index (r), ranging from positive (red: in-phase correlation), through zero (white: no correlation), to negative (blue: anti-phase correlation). The x-axis is the time of the timeseries, and the y-axis is the window size used for the correlation calculation, from the minimum local wave period (base of the graph) to the maximum period corresponding to the whole timeseries (i.e., global correlation at the top of graph). Only statistically significant correlations ($p \leq 0.05$) are shown; non-significant regions are masked. The global, maximum, and minimum correlation values are reported for reference.

In this example, a pair of IMFs from each time series is selected for cross-analysis based on their physical relevance and energy content. In this example, the fifth IMF (C5) from each time series – with characteristic timescales (~72–103 minutes) and explain a substantial portion of the variance (e.g., 60.5% for time series 1 and 18.5% for time series 2) – were chosen (Figure S1d) to compare using TDIC (Figure S1e).

In the left panel, Figure S1e shows the overlapping signals in the time domain while the right panel presents the TDIC output displayed using a color-coded correlation index (CI), where positive correlations are shown in red and negative correlations (or anti-phase correlation) in blue. The x-axis represents the time of the time series, and the y-axis shows the sliding window size (in minutes) used for calculating the CI, ranging from the local wave period (at the base of the graph) to the maximum period covering the entire time series (at the top of the graph). Global Correlation index (CI_{global}) for the whole time series and the maximum and minimum local correlations ($CI_{\text{max}}/CI_{\text{min}}$) are presented above each correlation graph. By analyzing the evolution of correlations over time, TDIC provides deeper insight into how these interactions change and adapt under varying conditions.

This integrated approach allows for detailed exploration of both the intrinsic variability of each signal and the scale-dependent temporal synchrony between them, facilitating physical interpretation of underlying processes across multiple timescales.

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